

Ayurvedic management of *Mutrakrichchha* with special reference to urinary tract infection: A Case Study

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Abstract

Mutrakrichchha comes under the disorders of *Mutravaha Strotas* and mainly deals with *shoola* (pain) and *krichhchrata* (dysuria)¹. Acharya Charaka has described eight types of *Mutrakrichchha*. Acharya Charaka has also mentioned 8 types of *Mutrargatha*. The above-mentioned symptomatology has close resemblance with urinary tract infections, as described in modern texts specifically lower urinary tract infections (urethritis and cystitis). Here we reported a new case of *Mutrakrichchha* (Chronic Cystitis), a 50 year old female patient consulted to OPD with complain of *Mutradaha*, *Adhoudar Shula*, *Sarvang Daha Anubhuti* for 6 years intermittently, this case manages with internal medicines *Gokshuradi Churna Phanta*, *Chandraprabha Vati*, *Gomutra Haritaki* and *Punarnava Arishta* which are having the common properties of *Shothahara*, *Vranaropan*, *Mutrarogaghna*.

Keywords: Cystitis; *Mutrakrichchha*; *Shamana Aushadhis*; Urinary tract infection

1. Introduction

Urine is an outcome product digestion of food and metabolism in the body it is passes through urethra¹. In both *Mutrarghata* and *Mutrakrichchha*, *Krichhchrata* (dysuria) and *Mutra-vibhandha* are simultaneously present but in *Mutrakrichchha* there is predominance of *krichhchrata* (dysuria)². In Ayurveda text the urinary disorders are described in the form of 8 types³. In *Mutrakrichchha*, the vitiated *Pitta Dosha* along with *Vata* (mainly *Apana Vayu*) on reaching *Vasti* (bladder) afflicts the *Mutravaha Strotas*⁴ due to which the patient feels difficulty in micturition. Healthy urinary tract is generally resistant to infections. Hence, for anatomical reasons female lower urinary tract is more susceptible⁵. Predisposing factors for recurrent urinary tract infection include female sex, age below 6 months, obstructive uropathy, severe vesical-ureteric reflux, constipation and repeated catheterization⁶. Poor hygienic conditions and environment, poverty and illiteracy also contribute to the increasing percentage of urinary tract infections. Urinary tract infections occur in 1% of boys and 1-3% of girls⁷. These infections are the common complications during pregnancy, diabetes, polycystic renal disease and in other immune compromised patients⁸.

2. Case Report

A 50 years old female patient came to Kayachikitsa OPD, Sane Guruji Hospital, Hadapsa, Pune, Maharashtra, India, with chief complaints of *Mutradaha* (Burning micturition), *Adhoudara Shula* (Lower abdominal pain), *Sarvanga Daha Anubhuti*. Patient was suffering from above symptoms for 6 years intermittently. She had used various allopathic

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medicines but nor cured completely. No any past surgical history noted by patient. The personal history of patient and findings were observed as noted in above.

2.1. Investigations

- Hb. 13.6%, wbc 17000.
- Urine-Pale yellow,
- Urine protein, glucose, RBC- Nil
- USG- cystitis.
- In abdominal examinations - soft with lower abdominal pain.

2.2. Treatment Plan

The patient was treated internal systemic treatment protocol treatment in IPD basis for 7 days. Later on, patient was discharge and treatment was continued for 30 days *Gokshuradi Churn, Phanta, Chandraprabha Vati, Punarna Arishtha* and *Gomutra Haritaki* tablet were used for oral administration for 3 months. Treatment was selected due to their properties of beneficial for treating *Mutrakrichcha*.

2.2.1. Pathya⁹

Purana Shali, Yava, Kshara, Takra, Dugdha, Dahi, Jangal Mansa, Mugda, Yusha, Sharkara, Kushmanda, Patola Patra, Gokshura.

2.2.2. Apathya¹⁰

Tambula, Matsaya, Lavana, Pinyaka, Hingu, Tila, Sarshapa, Masha, Karira, Ruksha, Amla, Vishamashana, Yanagamana, Vegadharana.

Table 1 Ayurvedic Treatment for *Mutrakrichcha*

Sr.No.	Drugs
1.	<i>Chandraprabha Vati</i> 2 Tablets TDS with water.
2.	<i>Gokshuradi Churna Phanta</i> 30 ml BD.
3.	<i>Punarnava Arishta</i> 4 tsp. BD with water.
4.	<i>Gomutra Haritaki</i> 2 tablets BD with water.

3. Result and Discussion

Patient had relieved from symptoms like burning micturition (*Mutradaha*), lower abdominal pain (*Adhoudara shula*), *Sarvanga Daha Anubhuti*, low grade fever (*Manda Jvara*), bodyache (*Deha Vedana*), general debility (*Daurbalya*) within the follow up period of 3 months. In USG findings cystitis observed before 3 month which was totally absent after treatment. No significant complication is evident during the course of study. In classical terms, it can explain that *Katu, Tikta, Kashaya Rasa, Laghu, Ruksha, Teekshna, Guna, Ushna Veerya, Katu Vipaka* and *Kaphapittaghna*¹¹. Properties of drugs are responsible to break the *Samprapti* of disease *Gokshuradi Churna Phanta*¹² acts as natural diuretic, anti-inflammatory, *Vata Kaphahara* that which subsides the symptoms of cystitis. *Punarnava Arishta*¹³ used in treating urinary diseases, abdominal pain, bloating, etc. *Chandraprabhavati*¹⁴ has anti-inflammatory activity, treating recurrent fever and relieves anorexia, urinary tract infections & pain. *Gomutra Haritaki*¹⁵ acts on *Mukha Rogas, Kushtha, Pandu, Krimi, Shopha* and it is *Kaphahara, Malanulomaka, Deepana, Vatanulomaka, Strotoshodhaka, Shophahara*.

4. Conclusion

The Ayurved treatment protocol with *Chandraprabha Vati, Gokshur Churna* and *Gomutra Haritaki* is effective in the management of *Mutrakrichcha* (Chronic Cystitis). The limitation of the study is this is single case study and need to be studied in a greater number of cases for its concrete conclusion.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that there was no conflict of interest regarding the publication of manuscript.

Statement of informed cconsent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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